

Deliverable 4.1

Training material for S-LCA addressed to decision-makers

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Abbreviations

CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
EU	European Union
FCH	Fuel Cells and Hydrogen
FU	Functional Unit
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	GreenHouse Gases
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
HYPOP	Hydrogen Public Opinion and acceptance
IFRS	International Financial Reporting Standards
IIRC	International Integrated Reporting Council
IP S-LCIA	Impact Pathway Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
moh	Medium opportunity hours
mrh	Medium risk hours
MSCI	Morgan Stanley Capital Investment
NFRD	Non-Financial Reporting Directive
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment
RS S-LCIA	Reference Scale Social Life Cycle Impact Assessment
SASB	Sustainable Accounting Standard Boards
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SHA	Social Hotspot Analysis
SHDB	Social Hotspots Database
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
USD	United States Dollar
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development

Executive Summary

HYPOP was launched with the aim of providing clear guidance on hydrogen technologies, facilitating effective communication, leveraging consortium expertise, tailoring approaches for stakeholder involvement, contributing to social indicators, and addressing barriers faced by ongoing projects. These aspects collectively contribute to the project's mission of fostering public awareness and trust in hydrogen technologies. This HYPOP Deliverable 4.1 helps to define frameworks for social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) for decision/policy-makers and citizens, while their application in two case studies (one on renewable hydrogen production in refuelling station and another on urban mobility) is addressed in HYPOP Deliverable 3.1. These frameworks are expected to serve as a valuable support for practitioners, decision-makers and other stakeholders when it comes to making informed and socially-oriented decisions concerning hydrogen-related systems.

This Deliverable 4.1 provides the frameworks subsequently applied in the case studies presented in HYPOP Deliverable 3.1 (M22, March 2025).

1 Introduction

In the landscape of sustainability assessments, integrating social and socio-economic criteria into life cycle assessment (LCA) traces back more than 30 years. In 1993, the SETAC Report "Conceptual Framework for Life Cycle Impact Assessment" (Fava et al., 1993) laid the foundation by proposing a social welfare impact category, and the term social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) itself was coined in 1996 (O'Brien et al., 1996). Recognising the necessity for addressing social criteria in LCA, it has evolved as a crucial methodology, particularly emphasising the "people pillar" within organisations, products, and services (Benoît Norris et al., 2020). The UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative established a task force by the end of 2003, actively exploring approaches for S-LCA. The initial Guidelines for S-LCA were subsequently published in 2009 by the UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative. Over the years, experiences, case studies, and publications in S-LCA have significantly expanded, contributing to a wealth of reference documents on the subject (Benoît Norris et al., 2020). S-LCA complements environmental LCA and life cycle costing (LCC) to provide holistic sustainability assessment. Although S-LCA follows the four interrelated phases reported in the ISO 14040 and 14044 frameworks (goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation), some aspects differ, are more common or are amplified at each phase of the study (Andrews et al., 2009).

Benoît Norris et al. (2013) introduced the methodological sheets for S-LCA. These sheets present a practical methodology for evaluating various impact subcategories. They include precise definitions, analysis of political contexts, identification of generic and specific indicators, and suggestions for reliable database sources to collect these indicators. In 2016, the World Business Council for Sustainable Development expanded its evaluation of social impacts, particularly in the chemical industry, by publishing "The Social Life Cycle Metrics for Chemical Products" (WBCSD, 2016). It is worth mentioning that the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), consisting of 17 goals and 169 targets, have gained significant recognition worldwide as a crucial benchmark for sustainable development initiatives. Among these goals, fourteen are closely linked to social impacts, which highly align with the S-LCA framework (Benoît Norris et al., 2020).

In summary, the evolution of S-LCA reflects a rich history of dialogue and development within the LCA community, aligning with global initiatives for sustainable development. This contextual background lays the groundwork for exploring and understanding the intricate interplay between social impacts and life cycle perspectives in the forthcoming discussion, as the report seeks to outline HYPOP's approach to the S-LCA methodology for evaluating fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) products. This report provides a detailed overview of the assessment procedure and presents a comprehensive list of social and socio-economic areas and indicators considered in the analysis of FCH products. The primary goal is to establish a robust framework for conducting S-LCA, emphasising the social and socio-economic dimensions. The report aims to integrate these criteria into the life cycle assessment of FCH products and format some structures regarding decision-makers point of view and reporting point of view, contributing to a more holistic understanding of the performance of FCH products as a complement to other social methodologies and tools (e.g. hazard analysis).

2 State of the art in Social Life Cycle Assessment

The S-LCA is a methodology that aids in assessing the potential social impacts of products and services at every stage of products life cycle. This covers every aspect, from acquiring supplies to contemplating about what will happen at end of life. Even though the general S-LCA framework (Figure 1) is based on that proposed in the international standards ISO 14040 and 14044 for LCA, each phase has some divergent elements (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*). It provides a framework for evaluation that incorporates data from both qualitative and quantitative sources. This framework provides information on social and socio-economic elements that support decision-making processes in an effort to eventually improve stakeholders' well-being. In particular, *Iribarren et al. (2024)* provided the latest guidelines on S-LCA of FCH systems.

Figure 1 Interrelated stages of the general S-LCA framework

2.1 Goal and scope

The goal of the study and the methodological framework are established during the first step of the S-LCA methodology, known as goal and scope. Assessing and evaluating a product's impact on society is essential for enhancing its social responsibility. It can be used to inform stakeholders about the potential impacts of a product, checking if it enhances the general social development of those connected to its supply chain. Determining the desired outcome type, identifying the stakeholders whom the results must satisfy, and the particulars of the challenges that need to be addressed will all play a crucial role in guiding decision-makers (*Benoît Norris et al., 2012*).

Defining the product system, its supply chain and its functional unit establishes the scope of the system. The functional unit is a quantified performance of a product system for use as a reference unit. The definition of the system boundary must endorse the goal of the study and consider each target phase of the life cycle of the product under study.

The activity variable is indeed a measure of process activity, and it is often related to process output. It is an essential concept in S-LCA as it allows for the evaluation of the social impacts caused by a process in a product system throughout its life cycle. The activity variable can be quantitative, such as "worker hours", which refers to the number of hours spent to produce a specific output, or it can be related to other quantifiable measures, such as the value added in each process activity.

It is crucial to define the stakeholder categories, their involvement, the impact assessment method that has been selected, the cut-off criteria, impact subcategories, indicators, data types, and data collection techniques that are pertinent to the study at this phase.

2.2 Social life cycle inventory (S-LCI)

The second stage of the assessment, S-LCI, involves collecting data on the unit processes within the system boundary of the product system. Organising data collection with a priority focus involves gathering both site-specific (primary) and general (secondary) data related to unit processes and activity variables. This comprehensive approach ensures context-specific data collection, allowing for a more robust and well-rounded analysis of the social impacts throughout the life cycle of the product.

At this stage, data accessibility often becomes a limiting factor. It is highly recommended to incorporate social and socio-economic aspects related to the production site. The collected data are then structured to create reference scales, which is one of the two approaches for impact assessment (the other being impact pathway). In this regard, it should be noted that the latest guidelines for S-LCA of FCH systems require the use of the reference scale approach for practicality reasons (*Iribarren et al., 2024*).

2.3 Social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA)

The third stage, S-LCIA, aims to compute, comprehend, and assess potential social impacts of the product system. Determining the approach for impact assessment and the social subject of interest, while outlining the requirements for the selected S-LCIA method, is crucial. Two S-LCIA approaches are typically distinguished (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*): reference scale approach and impact pathway approach.

- Impact pathway S-LCIA is generally confined to possible socio-economic and social impacts for a single stakeholder group and a very small number of impact subcategories. It is applied if evaluating the cause-and-effect chain's subsequent societal implications is the goal, or if predicting the consequences of a product system with an emphasis on assessing longer term potential social impacts.

- Reference scale S-LCIA techniques can be more suitable with the multi-actor viewpoint because they allow for the evaluation of all stakeholder groups and the impact subcategories that are associated with them. It is typically applied if social performance or social risk assessment is the goal for the product system. The latest guidelines for S-LCA of FCH systems require the use of the reference scale approach for practicality reasons (*Iribarren et al., 2024*).

The S-LCIA phase must take into account the stakeholder categories and impact subcategories defined in the first stage (goal and scope). In this regard, Table 1 presents an illustrative list of stakeholder categories and impact subcategories (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*), also including examples of social indicators.

Table 1 Illustrative list of stakeholder categories and impact subcategories

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	PSILCA indicators for one subcategory
Workers	Freedom of association and collective bargaining, child labour, fair salary, working hours, forced labour, equal opportunities (discrimination), health and safety, social benefits (social security), employment relationship, sexual harassment, smallholders including farmers	Child labour indicators: children in employment, male; children in employment, female; Children in employment, total
Local communities	Access to material resources, access to immaterial resources, delocalisation and migration, cultural heritage, safe and healthy living conditions, respect of indigenous rights, community engagement, local employment, secure living conditions	Local employment indicator: unemployment rate in the country
Value chain actors	Fair competition, corruption, promoting social responsibility, supplier relationships, respect of intellectual property rights, wealth distribution	Corruption indicators: active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery; public sector corruption
Consumers	Health and safety, feedback mechanism, consumer privacy, transparency, end-of-life responsibility	-
Society	Public commitments to sustainability issues, contribution to economic development, prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts, technology development, corruption, ethical treatment of animals, poverty alleviation	Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts indicators are (Risk of conflicts; Violations of mandatory health and safety standards)
Children	Education provided in the local community, health issues for children as consumers, children concerns regarding marketing practices	-

2.4 Interpretation

Interpretation, a pivotal phase of S-LCA, involves a comprehensive review of all preceding phases. The outcomes of the S-LCIA phase are checked following the conclusion of the iterative phase. The basis for inferences, suggestions, and decision-making that is in line with the defined goal and scope is provided by this analysis.

A thorough examination of each assessment step in the S-LCA process is part of the procedure's completeness check, which checks that all pertinent concerns indicated in the goal and scope are appropriately handled. Concurrently, the consistency check ensures that the procedures used in the inventory and impact assessment phases are used consistently, and that data is used consistently throughout the study, in accordance with the defined goal and scope. Next, a sensitivity analysis should be performed to assess how decisions and presumptions affect the outcome. Conclusions should be made once the study's significant components have been determined and the data have been carefully examined for consistency and completeness. This entails drawing attention to shortcomings and offering the decision-maker suggestions for measures to improve the scenario.

Interpretation within the framework of the United Nations SDGs could be an additional contribution, as they have gained international recognition from governments, businesses and organisations, and they have ties to all of the stakeholder groups and effect subcategories depicted in Figure 2.

<p>1</p> <p>NO POVERTY</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Fair salary # Poverty alleviation 	<p>7</p> <p>AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Access to material resources 	<p>13</p> <p>CLIMATE ACTION</p>	
<p>2</p> <p>ZERO HUNGER</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Access to material resources 	<p>8</p> <p>DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Freedom of association # Child labour Forced labour # Working hours # Social benefits # Local employment Fair salary # Contributions to economic development # Employment relationship 	<p>14</p> <p>LIFE BELOW WATER</p>	
<p>3</p> <p>GOOD HEALTH AND WELL BEING</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Health & safety (W&C) # Human health issues # Safe healthy living # Health issues for children as consumers 	<p>9</p> <p>INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Access to material resources # Technology development 	<p>15</p> <p>LIFE ON LAND</p>	
<p>4</p> <p>QUALITY EDUCATION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Access to immaterial resources # Education provided to the local community 	<p>10</p> <p>REDUCED INEQUALITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Indigenous rights # Delocalization & migration # Equal opportunity / Discrimination # Wealth distribution 	<p>16</p> <p>PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Legal system corruption # Prevention and mitigation of armed conflicts # Delocalization and migration # Access to material resources # Secure living conditions
<p>5</p> <p>GENDER EQUALITY</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Equal opportunity / discrimination # Sexual harassment 	<p>11</p> <p>SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Cultural heritage # Community engagement # Capacity building 	<p>17</p> <p>PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Public commitment to sustainability issues
<p>6</p> <p>CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Access to material resources 	<p>12</p> <p>RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # Fair competition Supplier relationships # Promoting social responsibility # Respect for intellectual property rights # Feedback mechanism Transparency # Consumer privacy end of life responsibility # children concern regarding marketing practices # Ethical treatment of animals 		

Figure 2 Impact subcategories linked to SDGs, based on Benoît Norris et al. (2020)

While Section 2 has focused on the current S-LCA methodological framework, Sections 3 and 4 place the focus on further specification of the S-LCA framework for FCH products in HYPOP with different target audience: decision-makers (Section 3) and citizens (Section 4).

3 FCH S-LCA framework for decision-makers

Decision-makers in organisations, particularly those involved in FCH systems, strive to avoid association with issues such as child labour or corruption, both within their own operations and throughout their supply chains. Concurrently, public authorities involved in FCH systems find value in applying integrated product policies, such as extended producer responsibility and public procurement. Consumers interested in FCH products express a growing concern for understanding the sustainability practices behind the goods and services they purchase or use.

The growing concern on social responsibility has brought forth the significance of S-LCA tailored to FCH systems (*Iribarren et al., 2021, 2024*), as it serves as a pivotal decision-making tool, offering insights into policy effectiveness (*Pryshlakivsky & Searcy, 2021*) and performance measurements specific to this field. In this sense, decision-makers in the FCH sector can leverage S-LCA to evaluate the social impacts of FCH products, making informed decisions that include social sustainability aspects besides economic and environmental ones (*Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024*).

Within the S-LCA four-stage framework (*Iribarren et al., 2024*), it becomes evident that information about geographical location throughout the hydrogen value chain is crucial. The assessment relies on both quantitative and qualitative data and indicators, carefully selected and related to interested third parties. For instance, identifying high-risk areas for child labour or evaluating the presence of transparency policies toward consumers becomes paramount.

Moreover, the definition of stakeholders and the consideration of their concerns are deemed essential throughout the S-LCA process. Workers, value chain actors, and various stakeholder categories are directly or indirectly affected, emphasising the interconnectedness of social impacts and decision-makers.

Such an approach involves modelling relationships between decision alternatives and lower order human needs (*Hutchins et al., 2009*), underscoring the need for a deeper understanding of these connections. A structured and well-established S-LCA procedure can help decision-makers understand and compare the social value of FCH products, enabling them to make informed choices regarding social sustainability (*Pollok et al., 2021*). Furthermore, it fosters the exchange of ideas about production and consumption across all aspects of society (*Dyson, 2024*).

Within this context, considering the specific progress in S-LCA made in previous projects funded by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership –SH2E (*Iribarren et al., 2024; Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024*) and eGHOST (*Iribarren et al., 2021*)–, Figure 3 presents the framework proposed in HYPOP for S-LCA of FCH systems with decision-makers as the target audience. Moreover, further details are given in the subsections below.

Figure 3 Proposed framework for S-LCA of FCH systems for decision-makers

3.1 Goal and scope

In the context of decision-makers, goal and scope definition entails determining the purpose of the S-LCA and making decisions about the details of the assessment to ensure that the S-LCA study is aligned with their specific needs and objectives, such as assisting companies in developing a targeted strategy for future social policy development, locating a social hotspot location and/or activity in the supply chain of the FCH product under study (Sala et al., 2016). Positive (e.g. job creation) and negative (e.g. gender pay disparity) social aspects could be relevant to the study. In order to facilitate decision-making processes involving varied stakeholders with varying interests, expertise and backgrounds, organisational aspects can be taken into account (Valdivia, 2021).

The scope defines the boundaries of the assessment, what it will deliver, and the components or features that make up the product system, providing decision-makers with a clear understanding of the extent and focus of the assessment. This includes defining the functional unit, system boundaries, data quality, exclusion of life cycle stages or inputs, and the selection of impact indicators.

The system boundary is a fundamental concept that defines the elements belonging to a product system and determines the system's scope. This boundary typically includes foreground and background processes in the product system. The purpose of establishing such boundaries is to ensure optimal decision-making considering product-specific supply chains. To that end, the use of the protocol for supply-chain definition developed by Martín-Gamboa et al. (2020) is encouraged, as implemented in the eGHOST project for FCH products (Iribarren et al., 2021).

A stakeholder category is a group that can be affected by the decisions made by companies involved in a product's life cycle. There exist several approaches for identifying the major stakeholder categories that might be impacted by a product's life cycle. Based on lessons learned in the SH2E project regarding the life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) of FCH systems (*Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024*), the method of choice for identifying the major stakeholder groups tapped for the product's life cycle is materiality assessment.

3.1.1 Materiality Assessment

Nowadays, industrial interest in sustainability-related topics is increasing and material issues, which often need to be included in sustainability reports, have significant implications for a company's risks and opportunities and are therefore critical elements for decision-making and strategy setting (*Fechner et al., 2019*). Conducting a materiality assessment involves the process of identifying, refining, and evaluating numerous potential environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues that could impact an organisation's strategy, performance, and risk profile. This type of assessment is typically comprehensive and may entail complex analysis to ascertain the significance of various ESG issues for the organisation's long-term success and value creation, catering to the needs of decision-makers.

The materiality assessment in FCH systems is essential for decision-makers as it provides a comprehensive understanding of the social implications of adopting and utilising FCH products, enabling informed decision-making and the development of socially responsible FCH technologies. This type of assessment gives insights that can guide strategies, communications and help organisations. Various methods obtained from literature include AA1000, GRI, IFRS, IIRC, SASB, etc. to identify top material topics (*Fechner et al., 2019*).

The concept of "double materiality" in the context of sustainability reporting and assurance refers to the recognition that a company's impact on the world beyond purely financial considerations can be material and therefore should be disclosed. This concept encompasses two dimensions: financial materiality and impact materiality. Financial materiality entails information relevant to investors, e.g., on value creation, development and performance of the organisation. Impact materiality is about information for various stakeholders, e.g., next to investors, also customers, employees, suppliers, and local communities (*Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024; Pihkola et al., 2022*).

With the help of materiality assessment, relevant stakeholder groups to address within the social dimension can be identified and selected. Stakeholder consultation as a starting point of materiality assessment is possible, if relevant stakeholders are chosen. Expert judgments, literature, and data availability are all factors to consider. The LCSA-related ORIENTING framework (*Pihkola et al., 2022*) states that materiality assessment can be built upon literature (e.g. previous studies, sector guidelines, reports, etc.) or stakeholder consultations and own estimations. The materiality assessment can be carried out with the support of the contribution analysis determining the share of social performances/impacts assigned to life cycle phases, processes, and/or stakeholders. The

contribution can be expressed either in terms of percentage contribution or qualitative ranking (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*).

Materiality assessments for FCH systems present a number of challenges that must be carefully considered (*Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024*). One major challenge is data availability and unpredictability, since acquiring precise and trustworthy information for many components of the system becomes difficult. Furthermore, given the developing nature of FCH technologies and the requirement for standardised/well-established methodologies, technical and methodological variances offer obstacles. Sustainability benchmarking complicates the assessment even more since defining comparisons for a technology with distinct features necessitates a deep knowledge. Adopting a life cycle viewpoint involves complications in capturing the complete impact of an FCH system across its life stages. Long-term strategy and materiality implications add another degree of difficulty, necessitating foresight and adaptation to account for the changing hydrogen landscape. To ensure the efficacy and dependability of materiality evaluations in the context of FCH systems, navigating these hurdles requires a deliberate and adaptable strategy.

Benefits of materiality assessment (Baum et al., 2023)

- It helps establish priorities.
- It assists with setting goals and targets.
- It builds a strong corporate value proposition.
- It informs a dynamic business strategy.
- It enhances stakeholder engagement and alignment.
- It leverages opportunity to create new revenue streams.

Challenges in conducting materiality assessment for FCH systems

- Data availability and uncertainty.
- Technical and methodological variations.
- Sustainability benchmarking.
- Comprehensive life cycle perspective.
- Long-term strategies and materiality impacts.

3.2 Social life cycle inventory (S-LCI)

The inventory data collection procedure typically hinges on gathering information about the worker hours per functional unit, with this working time functioning as the activity variable (*Iribarren et al., 2024*). The activity variable's data is derived from both site-specific statistics and databases, such as SHDB and PSILCA. Concurrently, data collecting extends to the assessment of social hotspots. This comprehensive strategy seeks to identify possible impacts and opportunities, so assisting in the meeting of corporate social responsibility (CSR) obligations.

3.3 Social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA)

Certain social issues of interest to stakeholders and decision-makers are covered at the S-LCIA stage (Benoît Norris et al., 2020). In the decision-making process of S-LCA, various stakeholder categories are considered to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of potential social impacts. The stakeholder categories typically include both internal and external stakeholders. Internal stakeholders are those who work directly for the company or are part of the organisation, while external stakeholders are individuals or groups that are in the value chain of the company, such as suppliers, customers, and local communities. Additionally, investors, shareholders, and governments are also important stakeholders in the context of FCH systems, as they can significantly influence the decision-making process and the realisation of projects. The goal of considering the stakeholder categories is to identify and assess the social impacts associated with the life cycle of the technology and to ensure that the assessment covers all relevant social aspects. This approach aligns with the best practices in S-LCA, which emphasise the importance of materiality assessment engaging a wide range of stakeholders to understand and prioritize specific ESG issues.

Regarding the evaluation procedure for the quantification of potential social impacts, the S-LCIA procedure followed in the eGHOST project for FCH products is explained herein (Iribarren et al., 2021). Thus, social indicators are estimated using the following parameters:

- i. The worker hours (WH) at each plant p within the supply chain, per functional unit.
- ii. The risk factor for each social indicator i and plant p ($R_{i,p}$, expressed in medium risk hours [mrh] or medium opportunity hours [moh] per worker hour).

Each social indicator (S_i) is therefore assessed (in mrh per functional unit) according to the following equation:

$$S_i = \sum_{p=1}^n (WH)_p * R_{i,p}$$

where n is number of plants included in the product system.

In this calculation procedure, $(Wh)_p$ is the activity variable. Worker hours are quantified directly or indirectly. If the plant-specific information is known, direct quantification is possible; otherwise, the indirect approach is used to quantify activity variable using the following equation:

$$(WH)_p = E_p * (WH)'_p$$

where E_p is the economic value (in USD) linked to each plant, per functional unit, and $(WH)'_p$ is the number of worker hours per USD for each plant p (e.g. found for the country and sector associated with the plant in the PSILCA database).

3.3.1 Social life cycle indicators

Stakeholder categories (SH_c in Figure 4) represent group types that can be affected by processes and activities involved in the products life cycle. There can be several impact subcategories (IC_k in Figure

4) within each stakeholder category related to a specific social or socio-economic aspect (forced labour). For each IC_k , various social indicators (S_i in Figure 4) can be proposed.

Figure 4 Illustrative structure of a stakeholder category

For instance, in PSILCA v. 3.1, four stakeholder categories (workers, value chain actors, society, and local community) are available, as presented in Table 2. The database includes 20 social and socio-economic impact subcategories and 70 qualitative and quantitative social indicators (Loubert et al., 2023).

Table 2 Stakeholder category and impact subcategories from PSILCA v.3.1 database, based on Loubert et al. (2023)

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory
Workers	Child labour, forced labour, working time, discrimination, fair salary, health and safety, social benefits and legal issues, freedom of association and collective bargaining
Local community	Access to material resources, respect of indigenous rights, safe and healthy living conditions, local employment, migration, GHG footprints, environmental footprints,
Society	Contribution to economic development, health and safety
Value chain actors	Fair competition, corruption, promoting social responsibility

The choice of social indicators to be considered highly depends on the goal and scope of the study, considering which social groups are affected along the product life cycle (stakeholder categories), which areas are relevant to the product (impact subcategories), and on which basis they are measured (social indicators).

3.4 Interpretation

In the interpretation phase, decision-makers are empowered to address specific social objectives by identifying critical social issues. When an input/output-based S-LCA is conducted, understanding the

structure of the analysed system and identifying the value chains that contribute most to the results can be achieved through a social hotspot analysis (SHA) (Benoît Norris et al., 2020). SHA quantifies the impact of an organisation's activities on society and helps manage hotspots within the supply chain of foreground and background processes. This analysis serves to communicate social impact to stakeholders, and meet CSR obligations. Hotspots are elementary processes or phases of a product's life cycle associated with significant potential social impacts, often linked to specific geographic locations. Key benefits of conducting social hotspot analysis in decision-making include:

1. Supply chain risk assessment: it provides solutions for companies assessing and managing the social risks in their supply chain.
2. Integrated business decisions: it enables responsible and integrated business decisions considering social impacts.
3. Critical hotspot management: it identifies and manages critical hotspots within a global supply chain.
4. Upstream impact assessment: it assesses an organisation's upstream impact on society through refined indicators (it uses a range of indicators to provide a refined understanding of an organisation's upstream impact on society).
5. Corporate social responsibility: it fulfils CSR obligations by addressing social concerns (companies CSR policies influence conduct of suppliers).

Subsequently, within this interpretation phase, multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) would be employed to prioritise and evaluate the identified social issues. It enhances the capacity to manage decisions involving a large amount of information, combine different indicators into aggregated results, and assign weights. This phase also enables the consideration of multiple stakeholders and interests, different types of information, and forms of data. Additionally, it fosters an analytical and deliberative process to generate options and management alternatives, as well as the evaluation of alternatives based on different criteria (Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024).

4 FCH S-LCA framework for reporting to citizens

In line with the trend towards sustainability reporting by companies (Klein et al., 2023), in the European Union (EU) there is a noticeable surge in citizens engagement towards sustainability, especially in seeking social-level information. This heightened awareness aligns with regulatory developments such as the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), which has applied to approximately 11,000 large companies. The recent introduction of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) significantly expands the scope to encompass up to 50,000 companies, including about 10,000 non-EU businesses, mandated to disclose sustainability information by 2026.

Notably, around 18,700 companies are voluntarily disclosing through initiatives like the Carbon Disclosure Project, demonstrating their readiness to provide critical information outlined in European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). This includes topics such as governance, strategy, risks,

opportunities, metrics and targets. The majority of these companies conduct at least some type of materiality assessment, indicating their position at advanced or mature levels.

The reporting procedures followed by companies to reach citizens have been increasing. This trend underscores the growing and influential citizen-driven movement towards sustainability, pushing companies to embrace comprehensive reporting practices. The role of large companies, particularly those publicly listed or financing themselves on financial markets and subject to ESG ratings like MSCI and Robeco, is crucial in the non-financial reporting landscape. Market demand and regulatory frameworks mandate high transparency standards across all company activities and data. Recognising this evolving landscape, Figure 5 presents the framework proposed in HYPOP for S-LCA of FCH systems with citizens as the target audience. Further details are given in the subsections below.

Figure 5 Proposed framework for S-LCA of FCH systems for reporting to citizens

4.1 Goal and scope

The motivation behind the implementation of this second HYPOP S-LCA framework is to evaluate an FCH product system for the identification of the corresponding social hotspots while assisting in reporting social results to citizens for awareness and social engagement. In this regard, the expected use of the results is to provide insights into the potential social impacts of the product system, which

can be used to inform citizens through reporting, improve social performance, and enhance transparency and accountability.

The choice of the most suitable modelling approach depends on aspects such as the technology readiness level and the manufacturing readiness level (*Iribarren et al., 2024*). Both positive and negative impacts along the life cycle should be considered, making use of site-specific and generic data that can be quantitative, semi-quantitative, or qualitative. In this S-LCA framework, in contrast to that for decision-makers (Section 3), materiality assessment is optional. In this regard, direct use of the lessons learned in the eGHOST project for FCH product system definition and selected social metrics (stakeholder categories, impact categories, and social indicators) is suggested (*Iribarren et al. 2021*).

4.2 Social life cycle inventory (S-LCI)

The proposed inventory data collection procedure hinges on gathering information about the worker hours per functional unit, with this working time functioning as the activity variable (*Iribarren et al., 2024*). The activity variable's data is derived from both site-specific statistics and databases (e.g. PSILCA database). At each tier, the worker hours per functional unit are directly or indirectly quantified for each block. When worker hours are not directly available for an entity, they can be estimated based on economic values by using country and sector-specific information from the selected S-LCA database (cf. Section 3.3). The use of the protocol available in *Martín-Gamboa et al. (2020)* for the identification of the sectors and countries involved in the supply chain is recommended (*Iribarren et al., 2021*).

4.3 Social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA)

The evaluation procedure corresponds to that detailed in Section 3.3. Concerning the identification of stakeholder categories, impact subcategories and social indicators, it is driven by the defined goal and scope of the study. In this S-LCA framework, literature findings from previous studies (*Campos-Carriedo et al., 2024*), particularly the eGHOST report on social metrics for FCH systems (*Iribarren et al., 2021*), inform the selection of default stakeholder categories, impact subcategories, and social indicators. However, other categories, subcategories and indicators might be added. This is consistent with general S-LCA guidelines (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*), which suggest an iterative refinement for their selection, comparing goal and scope and impact assessment phases when results have been obtained.

Based on the lessons learned in the eGHOST project regarding social metrics for S-LCA of FCH products (*Iribarren et al. 2021*), "workers" and "society" are selected as default stakeholder categories. Furthermore, Figure 6 shows the default impact subcategories and social indicators considered for the selected stakeholder categories, also depicting their connection to the SDGs. It should be noted that other stakeholder categories such as "local community" and "value chain actors", as well as other impact subcategories and social indicators, might be incorporated as the study advances, based on the supply chain definition and related social risks. Double counting issues concerning impact subcategories and social indicators must be avoided (*Benoît Norris et al., 2020*).

<p>1</p> <p>NO POVERTY</p>	<p>8</p> <p>DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p>	<p>Fair salary: Minimum wage, per month</p>
<p>3</p> <p>GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING</p>	<p>Health and safety: Health expenditure</p>	
<p>5</p> <p>GENDER EQUALITY</p>	<p>Discrimination: Gender wage gap</p>	
<p>8</p> <p>DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p>	<p>Child labour: Children in employment, total Forced labour: Frequency of forced labour Contribution to economic development: Contribution of the sector to economic development</p>	

Figure 6 Selected impact subcategories and indicators, based on Iribarren et al. (2021)

4.3.1 Stakeholder category "workers"

Based on the lessons learned in the eGHOST project regarding social metrics for S-LCA of FCH products (Iribarren et al. 2021), the impact subcategories "child labour", "forced labour", "discrimination" and "fair salary" are selected by default for the stakeholder category "workers". These are usually of particularly high relevance when dealing with multiregional supply chains.

Regarding social indicators, "children in employment (total)" and "gender wage gap" are chosen based on the available S-LCA literature on hydrogen systems (Campos-Carriedo et al., 2024). "Frequency of forced labour" is selected as indicator since it involves a broad spectrum also accounting for human trafficking, debt bondage, forced or servile marriage, and the sale or exploitation of children. This definition is consistent with the SDG target 8.7, which calls to "take immediate and effective measures to eradicate forced labour, end modern slavery and human trafficking". Regarding fair salary, "minimum wage" is selected as indicator since the established risk scale reflects the risk of having workers with a remuneration that is not sufficient to achieve minimum decent living conditions (Iribarren et al. 2021).

4.3.2 Stakeholder category "society"

Based on the lessons learned in the eGHOST project regarding social metrics for S-LCA of FCH products (Iribarren et al. 2021), the impact subcategories "contribution to economic development" and "health and safety" are selected by default for this stakeholder category.

"Contribution to economic development" is selected in order to assess the potential economic growth the involved countries could experience with the diffusion of FCH technologies. Thus, "contribution of the sector to economic development" is selected as a social indicator.

"Health and safety" is selected based on specific literature (*Campos-Carriedo et al., 2024*). This social area complements the aforementioned aspects and leads to address another SDG. In particular, "health expenditure" is selected as a social indicator, which considers public and private investment on health relative to the gross domestic product (GDP).

Overall, the social indicators proposed as starting point within the two default stakeholder categories are closely linked to central pillars of sustainable development such as human rights and economic development.

4.4 Interpretation

In this phase, the interpretation of social risks linked to the FCH product system is reported, incorporating methods such as SHA and MCDA, as outlined in Section 3.4. In this S-LCA framework, this is geared towards communicating the prioritised ESG issues that are of particular interest to external stakeholders such as customers, investors, and –especially– citizens. In particular, in order to enhance the accessibility of this assessment for interested parties, visualisation techniques are implemented. This focuses on key social issues and indicators that are particularly relevant to consumers and communities. These visual representations, such as infographics or summary reports, aim to simplify complex information and present it in a manner that is transparent and easily comprehensible to practitioners (which helps in detecting inconsistencies and relations) and broader audience (customers, investors, and citizens).

While certain tools have been developed and discussed in articles from a sustainability perspective, their application to social risks has not been extensively explored. Examples of these tools include the life cycle sustainability dashboard (*Traverso et al., 2012*), sustainability crowns (*Corona and San Miguel, 2019*), and the life cycle sustainability triangle (*Martín-Gamboa et al., 2024*). Despite their existing utility, these tools have inherent limitations. However, with suitable modifications, they can potentially be adapted to visualise and communicate social risks effectively.

4.4.1 Visualisation of social risks

In Figure 7, two different social indicators are presented as examples. One dashboard indicates the "Children in employment (Total)" social indicator, while another dashboard indicates "Minimum wage" as a social indicator. This type of dashboard visualisation makes it easy to locate the social hotspots for the respective processes involved in the system.

In Figure 7, for the "Children in employment (total)" indicator, "Process 1" contributes 50%, arising as the main social hotspot for this indicator. Conversely, for the "Minimum wage" indicator, "Process 3" contributes 38%, arising as the main social hotspot for this indicator. These social hotspots are visually highlighted with red arrows, directing attention to areas that require further focus.

Figure 7 Example of two different social indicators for visualisation purposes

5 Conclusions

Two frameworks for S-LCA of FCH products have been thoroughly presented in this report: one for decision-makers and the other for citizen reporting. On the one hand, the HYPOP S-LCA framework for decision-makers emphasises crucial features such as materiality assessment, social hotspot analysis, and multicriteria decision-making. On the other hand, the HYPOP S-LCA framework for reporting (particularly to citizens) specifies default stakeholder categories, impact subcategories and social indicators, and it integrates visualisation techniques to provide individuals with a better grasp of the social factors involved. Each framework is individually designed to meet the requirements and viewpoints of its intended audience. The proposed frameworks are recommended to be robustly integrated with LCA and LCC approaches in order to increase the depth and breadth of evaluations. Moreover, benchmarking with relevant case studies is advised for contextual clarity, with an emphasis on the use of visualisation tools for result interpretation. Overall, S-LCA is becoming an important approach for the assessment of FCH supply chains, but still with a strong potential for improvements requiring further interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary effort to robustly support decision-makers, citizens and other stakeholders such as policy-makers.

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